

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ASUNDI****FIRST NAME: PRATHYUSHA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly, but not the Premium version (provided by EUCLID)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 10

QUIZ

1. What is Plagiarism?

- a) using the exact information verbatim
- b) rephrasing the information given by another person
- c) copy-pasting information from the internet
- d) all the above without giving credit to the author¹**

2. Which of these is not a pluralized adjective?

- a) shoe rack
 - b) wet hands²**
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¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 19.

- c) fish tank
- d) attendance register

3. A graphic form that can compare segments within continuous data sets is:

- a) a pie chart
- b) a line graph
- c) a histogram³**
- d) an area chart

4. A working hypothesis one which:

- a) is a plausible answer that seems promising
- b) could be a possible outcome of the research
- c) is one that can turn into a claim
- d) all of the above⁴**

5. Working on topic ‘x’, to find out ‘y’, and understand ‘z’ better, is a three-part sentence that should:

- a) include a working hypothesis and the reasons supporting it⁵**
- b) state all the facts of the topic

³ Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 103.

⁴ Kate L Turabian, 31

⁵ Kate L Turabian, 33

- c) indicate the context of the research question
 - d) connect the references to state the claim
- 6. The correct use of abbreviations in a write-up/essay/dissertation is to:**
- a) elaborate in the parenthesis
 - b) mention the full form in a footnote
 - c) **mention the full form at the first usage in the text and continue with abbreviations in subsequent references⁶**
 - d) mention the full form and abbreviation together in the whole text
- 7. Positivism is an approach that is usually referred to as a scientific method and implements:**
- a) qualitative research
 - b) **quantitative research⁷**
 - c) both qualitative and quantitative
 - d) none of the above
- 8. A research methodology that involves collaborative and democratic practices to influence processes of change is known as:**
- a) grounded theory
 - b) the critical genres
 - c) narrative enquiry

⁶ Kate L Turabian, 353

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. (Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, 2018), 147.

d) **action research**⁸

9. **A well-crafted title for a dissertation conveys:**

a) what is under study and the mode of inquiry

b) central phenomenon of the study

c) main elements of the study

d) **all the above**⁹

10. **The legislation adopted under the treaties by the European Union is called:**

a) primary legislation

b) **secondary legislation**¹⁰

c) declarations and resolutions

d) none of the above

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 253.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 912.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed. (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2016), 73-74.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.